

The Twenty Eighth Case of Congenital Chevalier Jackson Syndrome

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi*

Children Teaching Hospital, Baghdad Medical City, Iraq

Abstract

Failure of relaxation of the upper esophageal sphincter with regurgitation of swallowed food into the pharynx occurs in a disorder called cricopharyngeal achalasia or Chevalier Jackson syndrome after the physician who first described it. A total of twenty seven cases of congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome have been reported in the world. The aim of this paper is to report the first case of Congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome (congenital primary cricopharyngeal achalasia) in Iraq which is the twenty eighth case in the World.

Introduction

Failure of relaxation of the upper esophageal sphincter with regurgitation of swallowed food into the pharynx occurs in a disorder called cricopharyngeal achalasia or Chevalier Jackson syndrome after the physician who first described it [1-3]. Chevalier Jackson (November 4, 1865 to August 16, 1958) was the first to describe cricopharyngeal achalasia in adults in 1915 [1,3]. Brown Kelly and Paterson in 1919 [2], and Vinson in 1922 also reported the disorder. Vinson when reporting the syndrome accredited Plummer for being familiar with it. Thereafter, some called cricopharyngeal achalasia Brown Kelly-Paterson syndrome, and some called it Plummer Vinson syndrome [2,3].

Childhood Chevalier Jackson syndrome (pediatric primary cricopharyngeal achalasia) is a rare disorder causing dysphagia during childhood. It is characterized by difficulty in feeding, regurgitation of feeds, and recurrent aspiration episodes [3]. Ardran et al. [4] were probably the first to report the occurrence of a congenital form of Chevalier Jackson syndrome in 1965. Five cases of the congenital form of Chevalier Jackson syndrome were reported during the 1960s; three cases were reported by Ardran et al. [4], and two cases were reported by Utian and Thomas [5]. Utian and Thomas [5] considered aganglionosis as the underlying etiology in congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome. Six cases of the congenital form of Chevalier Jackson syndrome (congenital primary cricopharyngeal achalasia) were reported during the 1970s; four cases were reported by Reichert et al. [6], and two cases were reported by Bishop [7] and Bondonny et al. [8]. Only one case of congenital cricopharyngeal achalasia was reported during the 1980s by Lernau et al. [9]. Three cases of the congenital form of Chevalier Jackson syndrome were reported during the 1990s; one case was reported by Skinner et al. [10], and two cases were reported by De Caluwe D et al. [11].

Ten cases of the congenital form of Chevalier Jackson syndrome (congenital primary cricopharyngeal achalasia) were reported during the 2000s; one case was reported by Raboei and Luoma [12], and two cases were reported by Mahomed [13] during the year 2000, one case was reported by Mathur et al. [14], four cases were reported by Muraji et al. [15], one case was reported by Korakaki et al. [16], and one case was reported by Erdevé et al. [17]. Five patients with congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome have been reported after 2010; one case was reported by Martin et al. [18], and four patients were reported by Drendel et al. [19]. A total of twenty seven cases of congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome have been reported in the world [3]. The aim of this paper is to report the first case of Congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome (congenital primary cricopharyngeal achalasia) in Iraq which is the twenty eighth case in the World.

Case Presentation

The case of Dania was studied when she aged twenty months, during November, 2015. Figure 1 shows a sketch of the facial appearance of the patient. The aunt of the patient, a dentist working in the field of medical education in the Iraqi Ministry of health asked me to study the case despite that the family had already consulted several doctors in Baghdad and Beirut and visited a teaching hospital in Baghdad, American Medical center and a French Hospital in Beirut. After many

OPEN ACCESS

*Correspondence:

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi, Children Teaching Hospital, Baghdad Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq, Tel: +964-7703930834; E-mail: almosawiaj@yahoo.com

Received Date: 12 Aug 2019

Accepted Date: 06 Sep 2019

Published Date: 10 Sep 2019

Citation:

Al Mosawi AJ. The Twenty Eighth Case of Congenital Chevalier Jackson Syndrome. *Ann Clin Case Rep*. 2019; 4: 1715.

ISSN: 2474-1655

Copyright © 2019 Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

consultations, the parents have not been told a clear diagnosis or satisfactory explanation for the child illness and the treatment given was considered unsatisfactory.

She had symptoms of dysphagia, choking, nasal reflux, excessive salivation that started after the first feeding during the first day of life. She developed aspiration pneumonia during the first week of life and she was hospitalized in a teaching hospital in Baghdad for twelve days and treated with intravenous antibiotics, and nasogastric tube feeding was started. After recovery of aspiration pneumonia, physical examination revealed no cardiopulmonary or neurologic abnormality.

During pregnancy the mother experienced bleeding during the first trimester and developed polyhydramnios. She was delivered by vaginal delivery at 37 weeks. At birth her weight was 3.25 Kg. She has an older six and half year healthy older brother.

This patient is the second reported with this disorder whose mother experience polyhydramnios during pregnancy. Because of the persistence of symptoms of choking with feeding and the continued need for nasogastric tube feeding, and the need for better therapeutic intervention and better understanding of the child illness, the family took the child to Beirut where they visited an American medical center and a French hospital in Beirut.

During the first three months of life several studies were performed on her in Baghdad and later in Beirut hospitals including:

1) Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) of the brain was performed at the American Medical Center in Beirut on the 24th of April, 2014. The findings were considered unremarkable. Axial T1, T2 FLAIR diffusion with reconstructed ADC map, coronal FLAIR; Axial sagittal and coronal T1 post gadolinium images of the brain were taken:

- a. The myelination pattern was normal for the patient's age and the corpus callosum was fully developed.
 - b. The ventricles and sulci were normal in size, shape and position.
 - c. There was neither evidence of intra or extra axial fluid collections nor any evidence of a mass or mass effect.
 - d. There was no abnormal signal or enhancement within the brain parenchyma and the diffusion images were normal.
 - e. The cerebello-pontine angles, cisternal portion of the acoustico-facial nerves were unremarkable.
 - f. The visualized portion of the para-nasal sinuses and mastoid air cells showed mild obliteration of the mastoid air cells.
 - g. The orbits were unremarkable.
- 2) Echocardiography of the heart showed normal findings.

3) Upper GI radio and cinema of swallowing was performed in the American medical center in Beirut on the 28th April, 2014. The study showed no tracheo-esophageal fistula, but there was passage of opaque product in the trachea:

During the barium swallow, barium was given through nasogastric tube which was withdrawn progressively during the barium injection. The esophagus had normal peristalsis and normal mucosa with no evidence of reflux or stricture. There was no evidence

of tracheo-esophageal fistula on this study. During withdrawal of the nasogastric tube, when the tube reached the hypopharynx, aspiration of small amount of barium occurred. When the barium was given by syringe directly into the oral cavity because the patient was having poor sucking, the patient experienced difficulty in swallowing, increased swallowing time causing the barium bolus to remain in the hypopharynx for prolonged time.

However, eventually the barium bolus propelled into the esophagus, and small amount of barium was also aspirated. This study confirmed the absence of any anatomic obstruction.

The barium study suggested that the possibility of functional abnormality in the swallowing process and the possibility of neuromuscular pathology.

In my opinion, the barium study gave a huge clue to the possibility of upper esophageal sphincter disorder namely cricopharyngeal achalasia which should be congenital as the symptoms started after the first feeding in life.

4) Larngo-tracheal endoscopy showed no anatomic obstruction and excluded tracheo-esophageal fistula.

5) Esophageal manometry and EMG of the swallow were performed during the 5th of May, 2014 at a French hospital:

A well-calibrated four channel catheter manometry with four pressure transducers spaced at three centimeters interval was used.

The pressure changes were recorded using a computer to interpret and stored data. The pediatric sterile esophageal motility catheter was passed through the nose into the stomach. After recording the gastric baseline pressure, the catheter was withdrawn to assess the lower esophageal sphincter.

Both the resting pressure and sphincter relaxation during deglutition were measured at the level of all transducers. A manometry of the esophageal body was used to assess the strength and duration of muscular contraction, to evaluate peristaltic activity, and to detect any motility abnormality.

Ten to fifteen wet swallows were given at thirty seconds intervals. Skin electrodes were also used to assess the EMG activity of the swallowing muscles and deglutition.

Findings of the esophageal manometry and EMG of the swallow included:

- 1) The pressure in the pharynx at 3 cm was normal and the peristalsis was normal.
- 2) The pressure at the upper esophageal sphincter was

Figure 1: A sketch of the facial appearance of the patient.

increased. Its relaxation was complete. In most of the time, there was cricopharyngeal incoordination with confrontation of the manometric pressures and the EMG activities. There was a delayed relaxation of the upper esophageal sphincter compared to the pharynx.

3) The proximal esophageal body had good propagation with good amplitude of the waves.

4) The distal esophageal body had good propagation with good amplitude of the waves

5) The pressure of the lower esophageal sphincter was decreased. Its relaxation was complete to gastric baseline level.

The patient tolerated the procedure of the esophageal manometry and EMG of the swallow without any problem.

The report of esophageal manometry and EMG of the swallow concluded that there were:

1) A cricopharyngeal incoordination with hypertensive upper esophageal sphincter.

2) Normal peristaltic wave of the esophageal body.

3) Low pressure of the lower esophageal sphincter.

Obviously, the first three items of the esophageal manometry and EMG of the swallow conclusion report were diagnostic of cricopharyngeal achalasia.

However, the doctor who wrote the report misled other physicians with forth item of his conclusion report by stating “No manometric sign of achalasia was demonstrated”.

Obviously, to be more accurate he should have stated “No manometric sign of lower esophageal achalasia was demonstrated”.

It is a matter of fact that the presence of cricopharyngeal incoordination with hypertensive upper esophageal sphincter is a good indicator of the presence of upper esophageal achalasia or cricopharyngeal achalasia.

The French professor at the French hospital in Beirut also stated in the hospitalization report “No manometric sign of achalasia”. Obviously, this statement was because of unawareness of the rare occurrence of upper esophageal achalasia or cricopharyngeal achalasia.

The therapeutic recommendations and interventions made at the French Hospital in Beirut included:

1) Gastrostomy for feeding.

2) Hemi-Nisson anti-reflux.

3) Swallowing re-education (Figure 2).

Discussion

Although there are few thousands of rare diseases identified, there is often limited professional knowledge and awareness of the manifestations of rare diseases and their appropriate management because of the small number of patients affected by each disease. Diagnostic challenges, diagnosis delay, misdiagnoses, inappropriate or unsatisfactory management are known to be associated with rare diseases. It is expected that more than one third of rare diseases are misdiagnosed more than once, or diagnosis is delayed for a variety of reasons [3].

Figure 2: Feeding of the child through the gastrostomy by a syringe.

Diagnostic studies in congenital cricopharyngeal achalasia include endoscopic exam of the esophagus, fluoroscopic contrast studies, and esophageal manometry. Esophagoscopy is useful mainly in excluding any anatomic lesion at the cricopharyngeal junction. In cricopharyngeal achalasia, a transverse sub-mucosal bar at the level of the cricopharyngeal muscle is present [3].

In contrast fluoroscopic studies, normally the posterior wall of the fully distended pharynx has a smooth contour. Findings in cricopharyngeal achalasia include [3]:

1) A minimal protrusion into the tail of passing contrast bolus to a horizontal, hemispheric or triangular shelf that completely occludes the lumen at the level of the fifth or sixth vertebral body.

2) Normal propulsion of the contrast bolus from the mouth into the pharynx is followed by weak or uncoordinated pharyngeal contraction with multiple attempts to force the meal distally by to-and-fro movements.

3) A dilated hypopharynx and delayed emptying can also be seen.

4) Aspiration of the contrast into the trachea and nasopharyngeal reflux may also be seen.

In this Iraqi patient, Tracheo-esophageal fistula was excluded by laryngotracheal endoscopy, esophagoscopy, and barium swallows with cinema of swallowing. However, the cinema of swallowing suggested a functional abnormality of swallowing. A definite diagnosis of cricopharyngeal achalasia should have been made by esophageal manometry and EMG of the swallow which showed the characteristic cricopharyngeal incoordination with hypertensive upper esophageal sphincter. The French hospital in Beirut discharge report stated that there was no achalasia.

The initial management of cricopharyngeal achalasia includes maintenance of nutritional status with use nasogastric feeding or gastrostomy if prolonged nasogastric feeding is required. The definitive treatment is cricopharyngeus muscle myotomy [3].

In this Iraqi patient the nutritional status was well-maintained with use of nasogastric feeding and gastrostomy.

Unfortunately, the obvious diagnosis was ignored and the definitive treatment with simple myotomy of the cricopharyngeus muscle which is known associated with high chance of permanent

cure was not considered at all.

Early surgical intervention for this disease is recommended to achieve early recovery from dysphagia and to establish buccopharyngeal swallowing during the appropriate period of development [3].

References

1. Jackson C. Diseases of the esophagus. In: Jackson C, editor. *Peroral Endoscopy and Laryngeal Surgery*. St Louis: Laryngoscope Co, Missouri, USA; 1915. P. 507-8.
2. Kelly A. Spasm at the entrance to the esophagus. *J Laryngol Rhinol Otol*. 1919;34:285-9.
3. Al-Mosawi AJ. *Congenital Chevalier Jackson syndrome*. 1st ed. Saarbrücken: LAP Lambert Academic Publishing; 2016.
4. Ardran CM, Benson PF, Butler NR, Ellis HL, McKendrick T. Congenital dysphagia resulting from dysfunction of the pharyngeal musculature. *Develop Med Child Neurol* 1965;195;7:157-166.
5. Utian HL, Thomas RG. Cricopharyngeal incoordination in infancy. *Pediatrics*. 1969;43(3):402-6.
6. Reichert TJ, Bluestone CD, Stool SE, Siekber WK, Sieber AM. Congenital cricopharyngeal achalasia. *Ann Otol Rhinol Laryngol*. 1977;86(5 Pt 1):603-10.
7. Bishop HC. Cricopharyngeal achalasia in childhood. *J Pediatr Surg*. 1974;9(5):775-8.
8. Bondonny JM, Hehunstre JP, Diard F, Bechraoui T. Cricopharyngeal achalasia, exceptional cause of dysphagia in newborn. *Chir Pediatr*. 1979;20(2):69-73.
9. Lernau OZ, Sherzer E, Mogle P, Nissan S. Congenital cricopharyngeal achalasia treatment by dilatations. *J Pediatr Surg*. 1984;19(2):202-3.
10. Skinner MA, Shorter NA. Primary cricopharyngeal achalasia: a case report and review of the literature. *J Pediatr Surg*. 1992;27(12):1509-11.
11. De Caluwe D, Nassogne MC, Reding R, de Ville de Goyet J, Clapuyt P, Otte JB. Cricopharyngeal achalasia: case reports and review of the literature. *Eur J Pediatr Surg*. 1999;9(2):109-12.
12. Raboei E, Luoma R. Neonatal cricopharyngeal achalasia: a case report. *Eur J Pediatr Surg*. 2000;10(2):130-2.
13. Mahomed AA. Primary cricopharyngeal achalasia in infancy: myotomy treatment of choice. *S Afr J Surg*. 2000;38(2):28-30.
14. Mathur NB, Banerjee S, Maria A, Bhatnagar V. Congenital cricopharyngeal achalasia. *Indian Pediatr*. 2001;38:783-8.
15. Muraji T, Takamizawa S, Satoh S, Nishijima E, Tsugawa C, Tamura A, et al. Congenital cricopharyngeal achalasia: Diagnosis and surgical management. *J Pediatr Surg*. 2002;37(5):E12.
16. Korakaki E, Hatzidaki E, Manoura A, Velegrakis G, Charissis G, Gourgiotis D, et al. Feeding difficulties in a neonate with primary cricopharyngeal achalasia treated by cricopharyngeal myotomy. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2004;68(2):249-53.
17. Erdev O, Kologlu M, Saygili B, Atasay B, Arsan S. Primary cricopharyngeal achalasia in a newborn treated by balloon dilatation: a case report and review of the literature. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2007;71(1):165-8.
18. Martin N, Prince JM, Kane TD, Goyal A, Mehta D. Congenital cricopharyngeal achalasia in a 4.5-year-old managed by cervical myotomy: a case report. *Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol*. 2011;75(2):289-92.
19. Drendel M, Carmel E, Kerimis P, Wolf M, Finkelstein Y. Cricopharyngeal achalasia in children: surgical and medical treatment. *Isr Med Assoc J*. 2013;15(8):430-3.